

Determination of the Second Dissociation Constant of H_2SO_4 from Measurements of E. M. F. across Cation Exchange Membrane

M. Adhikari, D. Ganguli, G. Biswas and D. Ghosh

Membrane electrodes, e.g., clay membranes and resin membranes were variously used for determination of ionic activities in aquo and aquo-organic media ^{1,2,3}. Presently an attempt has been made to evaluate the dissociation constant of relatively strong acids by such membranes,

$(a_{H^+})_2$ of H_2SO_4 soln. can be determined by measuring E.M.F. (E) of a cell of the following type, provided $(a_{H^+})_1$, is known^{1,2,3}.

from which HSO_4'

(degree of dissociation of HSO_4') can be determined from the eqn.

$$\alpha \text{ HSO}_4' = \frac{2(a_{H^+})_{\text{obs}}}{(a_{H^+})_{\text{theo}}} - 1 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where $(a_{H^+})_{\text{obs}}$ = observed activity of H^+ due to dissociation of H_2SO_4 & $(a_{H^+})_{\text{theo}}$ = theoretical activity of H^+ from completely dissociated H_2SO_4 , considering in dil. soln. molal activity coeff. of H^+ remains unchanged whether the dissociation of HSO_4' , ions is complete or not.

The value of $\alpha \text{ HSO}_4'$ substituted in eqn. derived by Wallace⁴ leads, to calculation of K_2 which is as follows.

$$K_2 = 4 \quad m \gamma_{\pm}^{2/3} \pm \left(\frac{\alpha_{\text{HSO}_4'}}{1 + \alpha_{\text{HSO}_4'}} \right)^{1/3} \left(\frac{1}{1 - \alpha_{\text{HSO}_4'}} \right) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Where γ_{\pm} = mean molal activity coeff. of H_2SO_4 of molality m obtained from literature.⁵

Where⁴ the principal assumptions are :

- (i) First dissociation of H_2SO_4 is complete;
- (ii) HCl is completely dissociated;

1. C. E. Marshal, *J Phys. Chem*, 1939, **43** 1155.
2. A. Bose, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.* **437**, 196, 605.
3. M. Adhikari, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 817.

(iii) Ion and solvent diffusion across the membrane surface are negligible in course of time of the expt;

and it is assumed that

(iv) for dilute solutions γ_+ value for a H_2SO_4 soln. of molality m remains approximately unchanged whether the dissociation of HSO_4^- ion is complete or not.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two types of cation-exchange resin membranes (i) Dowex 50 wx 8, (ii) Zeo-Karb 225 and one type of clay membrane – Padegaon H form heated 400-450° for 48 hrs. were used. Details of membrane preparations and experimental procedure were given elsewhere^{2,6}.

The obsd. E.M.F. values were reproducible within ± 0.1 mv and determined with a Leeds Northrup K_2 type potentiometer & Leeds Northrup galvanometer.

RESULT

TABLE—I

Temperature of expt. = 25°
Strength of HClO_4 = 0.001 m throughout
 a_{H^+} of 0.001 m HClO_4 = 0.001

$m\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$	$-\frac{5}{(a) \text{H} \times 10 \text{ theo.}}$	Obs. E.M.F. in mV by clay		Mean E.M.F.	$\frac{2(a\text{H}^+) \text{ obs.}}{(a\text{H}^+) \text{ theo.}} - 1$
		Membrane I	Membrane II	obs. in mV = E. obs.	
0.001	189.3	14.2	14.0	14.1	0.830
0.002	371.4	30.4	30.2	30.3	0.751
0.003	550.4	38.55	38.35	38.45	0.625
0.004	626.5	43.5	43.4	43.45	0.525
0.005	900.5	49.45	49.45	49.35	0.518

TABLE—II

$m\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$	α obs.	r_{\pm} (Ref. 5 1)	$K_2(\text{obs.})$ in mole $\text{Kg}^{-1} \times 10^{-2}$	K_2 at 25° in mole Kg^{-1}
0.001	0.83	0.83	0.78	0.01
0.002	0.751	0.757	0.88	(other methods)
0.003	0.625	0.709	0.74	
0.004	0.525	0.674	0.68	
0.005	0.518	0.639	0.74	

Av K_2 value = 0.76×10^{-2} mole Kg^{-1}

4. R. M. Wallace, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 3922.

5. Conway, "Electrochemical data", Elsevier Pub., 1952.

TABLE—III

Temperature of expt.	=30°
Strength of HCl	=0.001 m throughout.
a_{H^+} of 0.001 m HCl	=0.000965 at 30°.
γ_{H^+} of 0.001 m HCl	=0.965 at 30°

mH_2SO_4 $\times 10^{-5}$	$(a_{H^+}) \times 10^{-5}$ theo.	Observed e.m.f. in mV by resin membrane			$(a_{H^+}) \times 10^{-5}$ obs.
		Dowex 50Wx8	Zeo-karb 225	Mean Eobs	
134.24	252.5	22.9	22.9	22.9	232.02
201.36	372.5	31.7	31.8	31.75	325.65
268.28	495.0	37.3	37.4	37.35	403.54
335.60	615.0	42.5	42.4	42.45	490.60

TABLE—IV

m H_2SO_4	α Obs.	γ_{\pm} (Ref 5)	K_2 (obs.) in mole Kg^{-1}
134.24	0.8377	0.7975	0.0102
201.36	0.7485	0.7450	0.0084 K_2 (by other methods)
268.28	0.6347	0.7125	0.0069 =0.01 mole
335.60	0.5954	0.6850	0.0070 Kg^{-1} at 25°.

DISCUSSION

The value of K_2 thus obtained are considerably lower than value of K_2 anticipated and deviation from theo. value was less in very dilute solution where membrane electrode behaves according to Nernst's equation. Deviation in concentrated solutions were prominent and may be due to deviation of membrane potential from Nerst equation in concentrated solutions and furthermore due to departure from permselective behaviour of membrane in those concns.⁶

Department of Applied Chemistry,
University College of Science & Technology,
Calcutta University.

Received June 13, 1968
Revised MSS received May 25, 1969

6. R. M. Wallace—*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **71**, 1271

